

The Role of Women in Society and Stages of Leadership Development in New Uzbekistan

Aziza Sadridinovna Faizullaeva

Independent researcher, Tashkent state university of Economics

Article information:

Manuscript received: 28 Oct 2024; **Accepted:** 27 Nov 2024; **Published:** 18 Dec 2024

Abstract: The article is devoted to the study of the role of women in society and the processes related to the formation of leadership potential in Uzbekistan. It covers the legal status of women, ways to achieve leadership, their participation in public life, opportunities for adaptation to global and national changes, and the problems they face. State policy on supporting women, measures aimed at ensuring gender equality, and future promising proposals are analyzed.

Keywords: Leadership development, gender equality, societal role, legal status, social support, women's policy, education and professional development.

INTRODUCTION

The mechanisms are often used in our daily lives for protecting human rights and interests. These mechanisms serve as a key factor in maintaining gender balance and ensuring social stability. Human society is developing as a result of the interaction of social, economic and cultural processes. In order to ensure the sustainable development of society, laws and regulations adopted by the state must be effective in practice. In particular, gender issues and the empowerment of women have become one of the important directions of state policy.

Gender differences are often associated with the process of socialization. This process involves the acquisition of knowledge, norms, and values necessary for the formation of an individual as a full member of society. Socialization institutions - family, school, peer Group, surrounding people, including neighborhood relations, parents, and friends - play an important role in shaping relationships in society.

In addition, the role of women in society and leadership development is of particular importance at the global and local levels. According to the UN, the proportion of women in leadership positions around the world is increasing significantly, but there are still obstacles to achieving gender equality [1]. Therefore, public policies and public initiatives aimed at empowering women need to be further strengthened.

The range of work is being carried out in various fields to develop women's leadership skills, support their active participation in society, and address issues that concern them. This article provides an in-depth analysis of gender equality, the role of women in society, and the stages of leadership development.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

Influencing socialization processes are of great importance in the formation of society and determining its future direction. These factors are manifested, in particular, through the historical ethnic values, traditions and religious factors characteristic of the region. In each region of the world, these features are unique and do not repeat other regions. For example, the worldview and mentality of the peoples of Europe are fundamentally different from those of the countries of the East. Therefore, social processes vary across regions.

The processes of socialization in the countries of Central Asia also have their own characteristics. These processes are reflected in the mentality of the peoples of the region, in historical processes and in the social systems formed as a result of them [2]. The specific factors of Central Asia, in particular Uzbekistan, include traditionalism, loyalty to values, oriental mentality, family and marriage relations, and the dominant position of men in the management of society. Before the formation of the current modern form of these processes, there were various historical invasions and the influence of the colonial system.

During the Soviet Union, the social structure and lifestyle of society changed completely. After the collapse of the Union, significant changes were observed in all aspects of social life in Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, in particular, in the position of women in society. During the years of independence, state policy was focused on expanding the rights and opportunities of women [3].

Related to women were mainly manifested in the following areas:

- ✓ Political rights and opportunities to exercise them;
- ✓ Women's rights as family members and as individuals;
- ✓ Educational and vocational training opportunities ;
- ✓ Labor activity and employment problems.

The Uzbek government has made addressing these issues a priority of state policy. In the short period after independence, significant changes have taken place in the economic and social spheres of the state. The legal status and position of women in society have been significantly strengthened. The new political system is based on further strengthening the relationship between the individual and the state [3].

Direction of state policy was formed on the basis of democratic principles and aimed at guaranteeing human rights. Historical traditions, spiritual values, and folk traditions were taken into account in these processes. As a result, human interests and the needs of society were given priority in building a civil society and a legal state. These processes served as an important factor in strengthening the role of women in society. Uses historical and social analysis, comparative methods, as well as approaches based on the regulatory framework. This analysis not only aims to study the position of women in society, but also to propose strategic measures to develop their leadership potential [2].

In particular, Law No. 760-I of April 14, 1999 " On Additional Benefits for Women " Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan , August 29, 2003 " On the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan " Article 22 of the Law "On Elections to the Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan " , as well as the Law of March 2, 1995 PF-1084-No. " Women in the state and social construction of the Republic of Uzbekistan " Presidential Decree " On measures to increase the role of the Federal Decree No. 4245 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan " On the Social Rights of Women " additional measures to strengthen protection "About" and 2004- May 25, 2014, Resolution No. PF-3434 " On support for the activities of the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan " " On additional measures to support women" ensuring their rights , their participation in the political and cultural layers of society, Measures taken against discrimination against women's rights are a part of our independence. It has shown its effectiveness from its first years. These reforms have

been implemented in Uzbekistan in recent years. protection of motherhood and childhood, increasing the status of women in society, and strengthening the family A number of important decisions on strengthening: PF No. 5325 of February 2, 2018 [4].

“In the field of supporting women and strengthening the institution of the family” “On measures to radically improve the activities of the Federal Service for the Promotion of Education and Science” , May 25, 2004 No. 3434 “ Supporting the activities of the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan ” Decree” On additional measures and other regulatory. It is noteworthy that legal documents have been adopted [5].

In the Republic of Uzbekistan are yielding significant results in ensuring equal rights for women and men , strengthening the family as the basic unit of society, supporting the stability of marriage , and protecting motherhood and childhood. Determining the rights and obligations of parents in raising children is considered one of the important aspects of state policy not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the Central Asian region [6].

As a result of the reforms carried out since independence, Uzbekistan has become one of the most advanced countries in the region in ensuring gender equality and protecting women's rights. In particular, our country was one of the first among the Central Asian countries to join th United Nations Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination Against Women (CEDAW) in 1995. This convention was an important step towards combating all forms of gender discrimination and expanding the participation of women in society [4].

Today, reforms aimed at ensuring gender equality are continuing in Uzbekistan . In particular, various programs are being implemented to increase the participation of women in the economy, education, healthcare, and public administration. The activities carried out by state and non-state organizations in this regard are aimed at ensuring gender equality and strengthening social stability.

Uzbekistan’s gender policy is becoming an example for other Central Asian countries and is gaining importance in strengthening regional cooperation. International and local initiatives aimed at expanding the rights and opportunities of women are further strengthening our country's efforts in this regard.

RESULT

Ensuring gender equality and strengthening the role of women in society through development projects has become one of the main directions of Uzbekistan's social and economic development . Research conducted in the Central Asian region shows the need to identify the causes of gender inequality, eliminate them, as well as study the differential impact of development projects on men, women, adolescents and other groups. This process will help to further expand women's participation in society.

In Uzbekistan, women's labor market participation is 48 percent of the labor force and plays an important role in the country's economy[11]. In addition, reforms in the political sphere have significantly increased women's participation in parliament. If by 2013, the share of women in the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis was 22 percent and in the Senate - 15 percent, then in 2023 these figures reached 32 percent and 25 percent, respectively [12]. These changes are a positive result of efforts to ensure gender equality.

These indicators also compare favorably with Central Asian countries. For example, while the share of women in the parliament of Tajikistan is still low at 14.7 percent, in Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan this figure is around 23 percent [13]. Uzbekistan’s gender policy reforms are helping to establish best practices in the region.

In addition, programs aimed at expanding women's educational opportunities and increasing their economic opportunities in Uzbekistan are also yielding significant results. In particular, programs included in the “Women’s Notebook” and the National Strategy for Ensuring Gender

Equality continue to support women in the areas of employment, entrepreneurship and education. These initiatives serve to increase the well-being of society and ensure social stability [3].

In Uzbekistan are not limited to protecting women's rights, but are also creating an environment that encourages their active participation in all aspects of society. Gender equality and women's socio-political activity are considered one of the main factors in ensuring stability in society and increasing overall well-being. Therefore, the continuation of the reforms being implemented to ensure gender equality will have a positive impact on the sustainable development of not only Uzbekistan, but also the entire Central Asian region.

DISCUSSION

In 1995, at the World Conference on Women held in Beijing under the slogan “Peace, Progress and Equality”, representatives of Uzbekistan actively participated and joined the Beijing Declaration platform aimed at improving the situation of women [7]. This conference was an important step on a global scale in the issue of expanding women's rights and opportunities. In particular, the issues of gender equality and strengthening the role of women in socio-economic life were identified as one of the priority areas of this process.

Uzbekistan, gender equality is not only a social issue , but also a key factor in economic development . International experience, including research presented by the World Bank at the Special Session of the UN General Assembly in June 2000 , has scientifically substantiated the direct impact of gender equality on economic stability [8]. Uzbekistan continues to put these principles into practice , in particular, by implementing programs to ensure the economic independence of women .

Gender issues have reached a new level in Uzbekistan during the years of independence. The government of Uzbekistan has made the issue of women's development one of the priorities of state policy. The “Law on Ensuring Gender Equality”, adopted in 2020, is one of the important documents in this regard, which guarantees the active participation of women in public life. At the same time, the National Strategy on Gender Equality was approved in 2021, which set the goals of increasing women's participation in political and economic life, as well as overcoming gender stereotypes [9] .

Compared to other countries in the Central Asian region, Uzbekistan has made significant progress in achieving gender equality. However, gender issues still exist in the region. For example, the practice of “bride kidnapping” persists in Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan, while in Tajikistan, the dress code for women is controlled by the state. Such issues indicate that gender issues are still relevant in the Central Asian region [10].

Uzbekistan is seeking to strengthen international cooperation to achieve gender equality and create a model for the region. For example, in accordance with the provisions of the UN Beijing Platform, a number of projects have been implemented to improve social protection systems for women and children, and to ensure gender equality in education and employment. Opportunities created to expand women's participation in the labor market, including startup programs and vocational centers, are an important part of ensuring gender equality [7].

Addressing gender gaps and supporting women's active participation in society play a crucial role in Uzbekistan's socio-economic development. Continuing reforms in this area will also have a positive impact on the overall stability of the region.

CONCLUSION

the above information, measures aimed at increasing the equal rights and active participation of women in society in Central Asia, in particular in the Republic of Uzbekistan, and ways of their implementation are of great importance. In Uzbekistan, a number of strategic measures are being implemented to ensure gender equality, develop the professional and social potential

of women, and create conditions for their active participation in all aspects of society. In order to make these processes more effective, the following scientific proposals and practical recommendations can be put forward:

- **Updating or abolishing the concept of "female-specific professions": It is important to create opportunities for women to freely choose their professions and** overcome gender stereotypes in the process . It is also necessary to create wider opportunities for women to choose high-paying and responsible professions.
- **Expanding remote work opportunities:** Developing remote work options to balance household chores and childcare with work. This is especially important for young mothers.
- **Encourage creativity:** Involve women in creative activities in collaboration with non-governmental organizations, creating opportunities for them to develop at home. This will help develop women's skills and ensure their economic independence.
- **Legal and political education: Develop** special programs to increase women's legal literacy and involve them in political activities. New approaches are needed to increase women's participation in public administration and political careers.
- **Ensuring equality in family relations:** Developing mechanisms aimed at implementing relations between men and women in the family on the basis of agreement and resolving problematic situations based on the principles of equality.
- **Participation in child rearing:** Supporting women in finding their place in society by encouraging equal parental responsibility.
- **Combating violence: Strengthening the system of comprehensive** support by the state and society **for** women who have become victims of violence. It is necessary to create a comprehensive system of legal, psychological and economic assistance for them.

in Uzbekistan to promote gender equality and women's empowerment are not only strengthening the position of women in society, but also ensuring the socio-economic stability of the country . If efforts in this direction are continued, Uzbekistan can become one of the leading countries in the region in terms of gender equality.

REFERENCES:

1. United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) Gender Equality in Uzbekistan . (2023). URL: <https://www.uz.undp.org>
2. Mominov A.R., Tillaboyev M. A Human rights. Women's rights and freedoms international legal protection. //T . : Justice. 2013.- P.368
3. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 17, 2019 “Women and Men” Law on Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities
4. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev dated February 2, 2018 “On the support of women and the development of the institution of the family” Decree No. 5325
5. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev dated March 7, 2019 “Further strengthening guarantees of women’s labor rights and promoting entrepreneurship Decree” On measures to support the activities.
6. Mominov A.R., Tillaboyev M. A. Human rights. Women's rights and freedoms international legal protection. //T . : Justice. 2013.- P.368.
7. Saidov A. “International and national legislation on women’s rights” The main directions of development”, T.: 1999, p-82
8. Tansiqbayeva G. Eliminating discrimination against women – their necessary condition for effective equality//Women's rights and freedoms. – T.: Adolat, 2002.

9. UN Beijing Declaration and Platform for Action. (1995). URL: <https://www.un.org/womenwatch/daw/beijing/platform>
10. Achieving gender equality and enhancing women's economic empowerment". URL: <https://www.unwomen.org>
11. World Bank. (2000). "Gender Equality, Development and the 21st Century". URL: <https://www.worldbank.org>
12. The Republic of Uzbekistan on Ensuring Gender Equality. (2020). URL: <https://lex.uz/docs/4748825>
13. Statistics Committee. (2023). "Uzbekistan's Women's Labor Market: Analysis and Figures". URL: <https://stat.uz>
14. Gender Equality in Parliaments of the Central Asian Region. (2013). URL: <https://www.ipu.org>
15. Republic of Uzbekistan on Gender Equality. (2021). URL: <https://president.uz>